

Back

Demand - #123

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Request Type

Audit Demand

Protocol number

2193814217401

Subject Area

Regulation

Sphere

Federal

National Audit System Component

Type of Receipt

Date received

08/06/2022

Forecast of service in the unit

08/06/2022

Admissibility Criteria

Draft automatically saved

Activity already done or planned?

Sphere

Federal

Agency

Activity already done or planned?

Search in 1CP

Sphere

Federal

Agency

Elements

Local

Evidence of irregularity

Period

Documents of irregularity

Application attachments

Subject of the demand

Absence of elements

Competence

Is it the competence of the National Audit System (state/municipal)?

Sim Não

Is it a matter for other administrative bodies that have their own internal audit or supervisory powers?

Sim Não

Is it a matter of investigating the ethical or administrative conduct of a public servant?

Sim Não

Is the resource involved of federal origin?

Sim Não

Is it a request that requires first/second line management action?

Sim Não

Justification

Materiality

Volume of resources involved

Justification

The activity's realization cost-benefit

Low Medium Satisfactory High

Relevance

Social Interest

Low Medium Satisfactory High

Risk of not performing the activity

Low Medium Satisfactory High

Justification

Significance

Low Medium Satisfactory High

Timeliness of action in relation to the date of occurrence of the facts

Low Medium Satisfactory High

Analysis Conclusions

Accomplish demand?

It is suggested to accomplish It is not suggested to accomplish

Justification

Cancel

Send for adjustments